

PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED ENGLISH TEACHING TO STUDENTS- PHILOLOGISTS

Buronov Oybek Paygamovich

Orifov Khimoyiddin Kosimovich

Students of Termiz state pedagogical institute.

ANNOTATION: The article outlines some areas of professionally oriented teaching of English on the example of philologists. The main goals and objectives of the article are formulated. The relevance of the issue under consideration is indicated. The author emphasizes that the leading method in teaching professionally oriented English is the communicative method. In theoretical and methodological terms, this problem has not been fully studied, today many researchers and scientists are working on it. Some areas of providing professionally-oriented teaching of English to bachelors of philology are highlighted. The author refers to them: studying the needs of society in philological education, changing the content of education, which should contribute to the formation of communicative and professional competencies, as well as the creation of an educational and methodological base for the learning process.

The author introduces the developed teaching aids for the discipline "Foreign language" for the direction of training "Philology". On the example of philologists, it is considered how professional training can be improved by means of the English language. A significant role in the process of professionally oriented learning is played by special vocabulary. Since philology is understood as a set of sciences that study the culture of the people (language, literature, history, philosophy, art and their relationship), expressed in language and literary creativity, the study of philological vocabulary and terminology is a very complex process. The basic principles of teaching professionally oriented vocabulary and terminology, which contribute to the expansion of the vocabulary of the English language, are outlined. An important role is given to such content of education, which creates the need for the use of professional speech, writing, reading. It is proposed to consider in practice the integration of two academic disciplines profile and language.

KEY WORDS: professional sphere, university students, communicative competence, educational process, educational and methodological documentation, professionally oriented education, English.

ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО ОРИЕНТИРОВАННОЕ ОБУЧЕНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ СТУДЕНТОВ-ФИЛОЛОГОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ: В статье рассматриваются некоторые аспекты профессионально ориентированного обучения английскому языку на примере

студентов-филологов. Сформулированы основные цели и задачи статьи. Указана актуальность рассматриваемого вопроса. Автор подчеркивает, что ведущим методом обучения профессионально ориентированному английскому языку является коммуникативный метод. В теоретическом и методологическом плане эта проблема еще недостаточно изучена, и в настоящее время над ней работают многие исследователи и ученые. Освещены некоторые направления обеспечения профессионально ориентированного обучения английскому языку бакалавров филологии. К ним автор относит: изучение потребностей общества в филологическом образовании, изменение содержания образования, которое должно способствовать формированию коммуникативных и профессиональных компетенций, а также создание учебно-методической базы для учебного процесса.

Автор представляет разработанные учебные пособия по дисциплине «Иностранный язык» для направления подготовки «Филология». На примере филологов рассматривается, как профессиональная подготовка может быть улучшена средствами английского языка. Существенную роль в процессе профессионально ориентированного обучения играет специальная лексика. Поскольку филология понимается как совокупность наук, изучающих культуру народа (язык, литературу, историю, философию, искусство и их взаимосвязь), выраженную в языке и литературном творчестве, изучение филологической лексики и терминологии является очень сложным процессом. Описаны основные принципы обучения профессионально ориентированной лексике и терминологии, способствующие расширению словарного запаса английского языка. Важная роль отводится такому содержанию образования, которое создает необходимость использования профессиональной речи, письма, чтения. Предлагается на практике рассмотреть интеграцию двух учебных дисциплин: профильной и языковой.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: профессиональная сфера, студенты университета, коммуникативная компетенция, образовательный процесс, учебно-методическая документация, профессионально ориентированное образование, английский язык.

FILOLOGIYA TALABALARIGA KASBIY YO‘NALGAN INGLIZ TILINI O‘QITISH

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada filologlar misolida kasbiy yo‘naltirilgan ingliz tilini o‘qitishning ayrim yo‘nalishlari yoritilgan. Maqolaning asosiy maqsad va vazifalari belgilangan. Ko‘rib chiqilayotgan masalaning dolzarbligi ta’kidlangan. Muallif kasbiy yo‘naltirilgan ingliz tilini o‘qitishda asosiy metod sifatida kommunikativ metodni qayd etadi. Nazariy va metodik jihatdan ushbu muammo to‘liq

o'rganilmagan bo'lib, bugungi kunda bu borada ko'plab tadqiqotchilar va olimlar ishlamoqda. Filologiya yo'nalishi bo'yicha bakalavrlarga kasbiy yo'naltirilgan ingliz tilini o'qitishni ta'minlashning ayrim yo'nalishlari ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Muallif bu yo'nalishlarga quyidagilarni kiritadi: jamiyatning filologik ta'limga bo'lgan ehtiyojlarini o'rganish, ta'lim mazmunini o'zgartirish, bu esa kommunikativ va kasbiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishga hissa qo'shishi, shuningdek, o'quv jarayoni uchun o'quv-uslubiy bazani yaratish.

Muallif "Filologiya" yo'nalishi bo'yicha "Chet tili" faniga oid ishlab chiqilgan o'quv qo'llanmalarni taqdim etadi. Filologlar misolida ingliz tili vositasida kasbiy tayyorgarlikni qanday takomillashtirish mumkinligi ko'rib chiqilgan. Kasbiy yo'naltirilgan o'qitish jarayonida maxsus lug'at muhim rol o'ynaydi. Filologiya xalq madaniyatini (til, adabiyot, tarix, falsafa, san'at va ularning o'zaro bog'liqligini) o'rganadigan fanlar majmui sifatida qaralishi sababli, filologik lug'at va terminologiyani o'rganish juda murakkab jarayondir. Kasbiy yo'naltirilgan lug'at va terminologiyani o'qitishning asosiy tamoyillari, ingliz tilidagi so'z boyligini kengaytirishga yordam beruvchi usullar bayon qilingan. Ta'lim mazmuniga professional nutq, yozish va o'qish zaruriyatini yaratadigan sharoitlar kiritilgan. Amaliyotda profil va tilga oid ikki akademik fan integratsiyasini ko'rib chiqish taklif etiladi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: kasbiy soha, universitet talabalari, kommunikativ kompetensiya, ta'lim jarayoni, o'quv-uslubiy hujjatlar, kasbiy yo'naltirilgan ta'lim, ingliz tili.

Statement of the problem in general terms and its connection with important scientific and practical problems. At this stage of the development of society, the professional orientation of teaching university students becomes the most significant and priority. Proficiency in a foreign language at a level sufficient for professional communication in the professional field is one of the requirements of modern society for university graduates and is an indispensable component of their professional training. Students' understanding of the role of the English language in their future professional activities makes it motivated to study it in depth.

The learning process can be subordinated to a certain algorithm, which contains the whole complex of methodological techniques and teaching aids that are adequate to the goals and conditions of learning. Analysis of recent studies and publications that dealt with aspects of this problem and on which the author bases himself; highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. The essence of professional foreign language training lies in the formation and development of abilities for foreign language communication through the integration of approaches to creating a foreign

language professionally oriented educational environment at the university [1]. A large number of scientific works touch upon the essence of this approach and its aspects.

Career-oriented teaching of English originated as a scientific direction in the 1960s abroad. The analysis and development of a theoretical framework in the field of theory and methods of teaching foreign languages was carried out by such scientists as: N.I. Almazova, T.M. Balykhina, I.L. Beam, P.B. Gurvich, A.D. Deikin, R.P. Milrud, E.I. Passov, O.G. Polyakov, G.V. Rogova, Yu.E. Prokhorov, G.G. Sokolova, S.K. Folomkina, A.N. Shamov, S.F. Shatilov, A.V. Shchepilova, A.N. Schukin and others [2]. Today, a lot of work is being done to optimize the educational process and methods of teaching English.

Scientists, researchers, and practitioners analyze the state of affairs, specify the requirements for methodological developments, and create educational and methodological complexes. But, agreeing with the point of view of many scientists, it should be noted that the concept of professionally oriented teaching of the English language has not yet been fully formed. We find an explanation for this fact in the insufficient development of the designated problem in theoretical and methodological terms, which puts it in the category of topical ones. The problem of the professional orientation of teaching by means of a foreign language has yet to be solved.

It is necessary to radically change approaches to the organization of language training; without this, it is not possible to expect a significant improvement in the level of preparedness within the time allotted by the program and on the existing educational and methodological basis. Formation of the goals of the article. The purpose of this article is to consider some areas of providing professionally-oriented teaching of the English language on the example of philologists.

Presentation of the main research material with substantiation of the obtained scientific results. The key method in teaching professionally oriented English is the communicative method, which is based on the idea that the language is used for communication, therefore, the goal of teaching a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence.

This means that a modern student must master the terminology and basics of speech professional culture, technologies for extracting information from professional texts. Mastering English terminology in the professional field is a difficult methodological task, complicated by the lack and incompleteness of industry-specific translation dictionaries and relevant terminological standards. Studies have shown that the main principles of teaching professionally oriented vocabulary are:

- didactic (visibility, interdisciplinary integration);
- psychological (stages in the formation of lexical skills and abilities);

- methodical (learning vocabulary in various types of speech activity, a differentiated approach depending on the purpose of learning vocabulary) [3].

Compliance with the above principles allows students to master a certain set of lexical units (a thematic dictionary that displays the key concepts and terms of the philological field), syntactic and grammatical categories specific to scientific literature, the ability to abstract and annotate what they have read, turns of speech and clichés typical for oral communication in a professional circle. (presentations, symposiums, conferences, joint work on projects, communication on the workflow with colleagues from other countries), the ability to understand the above elements by ear [4].

We have identified the following areas for providing professionally-oriented teaching of English to bachelors of philology: analysis of current philological problems, study of the educational needs of society, updating the content of education, creating educational and methodological documentation of the learning process, which includes work programs of disciplines, textbooks, teaching aids, workshops, work notebooks, methods, etc. Let us dwell on the educational and methodological component of the educational process, the creation of which is preceded by: research work [5], study of the experience of other universities, preparation and analysis of scientific articles on this issue [6-11], consideration of the structure and content of the available material, accumulation of information.

As a result of this approach, the educational process for the direction of training "Philology" in the discipline "Foreign Language" is provided both with a basic textbook, which is one of the defining teaching aids, and supplemented by the author's developments. The author's component is specially developed teaching aids that contribute to the formation of a whole range of communicative and professionally oriented competencies in students. The most important criterion in creating a manual for teaching professional English, we consider the availability of the proposed material, as well as the use of such training tasks and techniques that make it possible to develop speech skills [12].

Thus, in the work program of the discipline "Foreign Language" of the direction of preparation "Philology", which is studied in the first year, it is recommended to use:

– an electronic educational and methodological manual "English Grammar" in three parts, which deals with all grammatical categories and uses an integrative approach

- comparison of Russian and English grammar. The manual is up-to-date, exercises are selected for each topic, allowing you to check the degree of assimilation of the material, there are links in the text, after passing which you can get additional information on the topic and pass the test;

– electronic workshop "English for philologists", designed to expand professional vocabulary and terminology.

The selected literary texts (fragments of the works of English classics), which are of great importance in the professionally oriented education of philologists, and the proposed tasks for them allow to activate the vocabulary of students, expand the possibilities of analyzing the means of artistic expression. At present, work on the creation of educational and methodological documentation for professionally oriented teaching of English to bachelors of philology has not been completed.

At the stage of development and collection of material, information, there are two more manuals that will significantly expand the capabilities of the existing base and will contribute to the formation of lexical skills. These are the educational and methodological manual "English terminology for philologists" and "Collection of professional texts for philologists (in English)". The main task of these manuals is to create situations that determine the need to use professional speech [4].

Special vocabulary plays a significant role in this approach of teaching. Philological terminology seems to be diverse, quite complex, covers many areas of life and has its own characteristics and features. Today, while working on the manual "English terminology for philologists", we study scientific works in the field of philological and linguistic education, discourse, use the capabilities of Internet search engines [13–15], consider glossaries of terms in philology and linguistics, on the methodology of teaching English, we are working on dictionaries of philological and linguistic terms, etc. [16–18].

Philology students are involved in such search and research work. The use of elements of analysis in the educational process allows students to expand their skills in working with lexical material and move to the level of ability to operate with a specific professional term and consciously apply it. Thus, the content of teaching English is closely related to professional training at the university, it must be formed by selecting each methodological and content component, taking into account the direction of training of students and to help them master it [19].

The topics studied should be of a profiling nature, the vocabulary should include a large amount of professional terminology, and tasks should be aimed at mastering professional vocabulary. The next direction in providing professionally-oriented teaching of the English language is the expansion of interdisciplinary links between the English language and other disciplines of professional orientation.

In [20], we emphasized the possibility of a wide use of the integration of academic disciplines, which implies the study of certain issues of special disciplines in a foreign language. It is logical to assume that the creation of professional foreign language training for university students will be reduced to the introduction of

interdisciplinary integration. A foreign language is a tool that allows, on the one hand, to master a foreign language, on the other hand, to learn a profession through language [21].

Having considered the curriculum of the bachelor's program in the field of study "Philology", having determined the structural and logical connections of the disciplines of the profile and language cycle, it seems possible to us to integrate the academic discipline "History of Foreign Literature", which is studied in the first two years of study, and the disciplines "Foreign Language" or "English in the field of professional communication", coinciding in terms of training. Such integration involves the study by students of English classical and modern literature in English.

This process should be ensured by the teachers of the foreign language department, and here the interdisciplinary alliance and cooperation of the departments is very important. Considering the above, we emphasize that as a result of professionally oriented learning of a foreign language, lexical skills, skills of reading professional documentation, skills of oral and written speech are formed [22-26].

Conclusions of the study and prospects for further research in this area. We have considered some areas of providing professionally-oriented teaching of English to bachelors of philology, highlighting among them the creation of new approaches and methods in the educational process, allowing the formation of communicative and professional competencies, the development of professionally-oriented teaching materials for each area of training, allowing to develop speech skills, full-scale establishment of interdisciplinary connections.

Understanding and taking into account the results of the analysis and the achievements of the pedagogical experience of previous generations will contribute to the widespread introduction of the integration of various methods, ideas and approaches in education, and will make the process of learning English professionally oriented.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Zvyagintseva E.P., Valiakhmetova L.V. Integrative-developing approach in the course of foreign language training of university students as one of the promising vectors of the educational process // Prospects of Science. 2014. No. 9 (60). pp. 38–41.
2. Poltavets I.D. Formation of Comparative Analysis Skills in Philology Students: Abstract of the thesis. ... Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences / Nizhny Novgorod State Linguistic University. Nizhny Novgorod, 2012
3. Vilensky M.Ya., Obratsov P.I., Uman A.I. Technology of professionally oriented education in higher education. Eagle: OSU, 2010. 270 p.
4. Shaimova G. A., Shavkueva D. Sh. Vocational-oriented teaching of English in non-linguistic universities // Young scientist. 2013. No. 11. S. 692–694.

5. Adamko M.A. Formation of professional competence of students of the direction of preparation of bachelors "Philology" on the basis of an integrative approach: abstract of dis. ... Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences / Togliatti State University. Togliatti, 2013.

6. Adamko M.A. Analysis of the results of the study of the process of formation of professional competence among students - philologists on the basis of an integrative approach. Vector of Science of Togliatti State University. 2014. No. 1 (27). pp. 193–197.

7. Adamko M.A. Features of teaching English at the university in modern conditions // Vector of Science of Togliatti State University. 2015. No. 3-2 (33-2). pp. 283–288.

8. Smirnova E.V. Didactic goals of using information technology tools for the development of foreign language skills in the process of teaching English // Karelian scientific journal. 2014. No. 4. S. 82-88.

9. Egorseva N.A., Sidorkina N.V. The value of role-playing games in teaching English // Azimuth of scientific research: pedagogy and psychology. 2016. V. 5. No. 1 (14). pp. 49-52.

10. Buldina I.A. Basic principles of teaching speaking in a foreign language (English) to students of non-linguistic specialties of the university with different levels of training // Karelian scientific journal. 2016. V. 5. No. 4 (17). pp. 9-12.

11. Zonova M.V., Nikolaeva N.A., Sosnina N.G. Formation of managerial skills of the future manager of the service industry in the process of participation in project activities in English // Azimut of scientific research: pedagogy and psychology. 2017. V. 6. No. 4 (21). pp. 197-201.

12. Adamko M.A. The technology of integrative learning in the formation of general professional competence "Philological analysis and interpretation of a literary text" among students-philologists // Vector of Science of Togliatti State University. 2012. No. 3. S. 215–218.

13. Polenova A.Yu. The problem of written discourse and the possibility of its use in the educational process of the university // Culture. The science. Integration. 2011. No. 3. S. 68–72.

14. Balykhina T.M. Structure and content of Russian philological education. Methodological problems of teaching the Russian language: scientific publication. M.: MGUP, 2000. S. 39.

15. Bagramova N.V. On the combination of innovations and trends in teaching foreign languages in the context of the Bologna process // Foreign languages in economic universities in Russia. 2005. No. 4. S. 37–41.

16. Khvorostin D. English-Russian Dictionary of Linguistic Terms. Chelyabinsk, 2007. 113 p.
17. Zhrebilo T.V. Dictionary of linguistic terms. Nazran: Pilgrim, 2010. 486 p.
18. Akhmatova O.S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. M.: Editorial. URSS, 2004. 576 p.
19. Bezrukova V.S. Pedagogy: textbook. Rostov n / D .: Phoenix, 2013. 381 p.
20. Adamko M.A. Integrating academic disciplines as one of the ways to improve the effectiveness of teaching English at a university // Azimut of Scientific Research: Pedagogy and Psychology. 2016. V. 5. No. 4 (17). pp. 17–20.
21. Marsh D. Content and Language Integrating Learning (CLIL). A Development Trajectory. Cordoba: University of Cordoba, 2012. 554 p.
22. Smirnova E.V. Individual-psychological aspect in teaching a foreign language when using electronic means of educational purposes // Azimut of scientific research: pedagogy and psychology. 2016. V. 5. No. 4 (17). pp. 408-411.
23. Bobrova N.V. Difficulties of profile-oriented teaching of English in a technical university // Privolzhsky Scientific Bulletin. 2015. No. 4-2 (44). pp. 37–40.
24. Khokhlenkova L.A. The advantages of the project method in teaching a foreign language to future specialists in tourist destinations in service universities // Azimut of Scientific Research: Pedagogy and Psychology. 2016. V. 5. No. 2 (15). pp. 171-174.
25. Blieva Zh.M., Khosroeva N.I. Foreign language as a subject and speech in the formation of a multicultural worldview of environmental students // Azimut of scientific research: pedagogy and psychology. 2016. V. 5. No. 4 (17). pp. 74-78.
26. Rudneva T.I., Khramtsova A.B. Influence of foreign language means on the dynamics of students' professional motives // Samara Scientific Bulletin. 2016. No. 4 (17). pp. 216-220.

